

Elements, Ways and Sources Of Environmental Pollution By Oil and Gas

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 28, 2021

Accepted:
October 30, 2021

Keywords :

Oil and Gas, pollution,
nature, soil, air, water

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5639343

Abstract

This study deals with the elements of environmental pollution such as oil and gas. The components of the environment represented by soil, air or water are affected by pollution. This causes an imbalance in the environment. People who legally conduct nuclear tests and the spread of dust that results from explosions. Forms of pollution vary according to the nature of the environment in which it is produced. There is pollution that affects water, air and soil, and the sources of environmental pollution have also varied, including fires, oil well fires, oil leaks, and many agreements are held to reduce marine pollution.

Introduction

Oil and gas pollution is one of the different types which affects our environment. The more polluted the ocean in which man lives, the more dangerous it becomes. It becomes widespread because of different reasons including; technological acceleration, emissions of gases, explosions, leakage into the seas and oceans, and the excessive use of natural resources. Many laws and agreements are held to reduce pollution of seas and oceans. The sources of pollution have varied which include oil and gas refining, fires that negatively affect the environment, soil and air pollution from factories and have numerous damages.

Problem of the study

The main problem of this study lies in the increase of cases in oil and gas pollution, and it is determined as follows:

- 1- What are the elements of environmental pollution, oil and gas?
- 2- Do the different ways of environmental pollution have an impact on the environment ?
- 3- What are the sources of environmental pollution ?

Hypothesis of the study

The hypothesis is to find a preliminary solution to the problem:

- 1- There are many elements that affect the environment, whether it is the natural environment or people with legal authority.
- 2- The forms of environmental pollution have an influential role on the environment which include; air, water and soil pollution.
- 3- The sources of environmental pollution: oil and gas refining, fires, explosions and oil leaks play an influential role on the environment .

Significance of the study

The significance of the study lies in that nowadays oil and gas environmental pollution becomes an issue that attracts politicians and laws to protect the environment and reduce this phenomenon.

Objectives of the study

The research aims at the following points:

- 1- Highlight the factors affecting environmental oil and gas pollution.
- 2- Knowing the different forms and sources of environmental pollution with oil and gas.
- 3- Shedding light on the scale and severity of oil and gas pollution on the environment.

Research Methodology :this study is based on the following:

- 1- **The analytical approach** : is based on the analysis and discussion of the presented idea in the light of appropriate opinions. Thus, it can be attributed to the legislative text that treats it, if any, and to the jurisprudential opinion on which it is based. The study also relies on the analysis of legal provisions.
- 2- **Applied approach**: is based on the basis of reliance on the positions of the judiciary regarding the problem under study.

First: Elements of environmental pollution by oil and gas:

We concluded that pollution refers to any liquid, solid, or gaseous substance, noise, thermal radiation, or the like that exist in an unnatural quantity or manner that leads directly or indirectly to harm to humans and all other living and non-living organisms that exist in the environment.

First: Bringing polluting materials in the environment or the natural environment:

This medium represents the components of the environment, whether soil, air or water. This change begins with an imbalance in the innate or natural balance between the elements and components of the environment. This type of pollution is caused by bringing polluting substances, whatever their nature is liquid, solid or gaseous, energy whether thermal or radioactive in the immediate environment. These substances are called pollutants, and they are substances or energy that enter the environment, causing disturbances in the various ecosystems and resulting in many damages to living organisms. ⁽¹⁾

Second: Bringing is made by a legal person:

There must be a person that exerts its influence in effecting that change directly or indirectly. It is usually said that that hand is a person, for example, conducting nuclear tests and the spread of dust produced by these explosions to remote areas, as well as factory fumes, and the emptying of toxic waste into water seas and oceans or burying waste in the ground. ⁽²⁾

It is worth noting that pollution result from fate and destiny acts of god such as earthquakes, volcanoes, floods, and others, as well as causing pollution that results in an environmental disaster, but the law does not have an impact on them except within the limits of obligating the state to compensate those affected and face the effects arising from it. ⁽³⁾

Third: If the entry results in or is likely to cause damage to the environment

These results are represented in the elimination of some of the natural components and elements of the environment and necessary for human life, as well as all other living organisms. The lesson is the result of the change from the work of the legal person. This harm is reflected on the human and living and non-living organisms, and this quantitative change may be such as an increase in the addition of some components. The natural environment, such as an increase in carbon dioxide, and the change may also be qualitative, such as adding compounds that are foreign to natural systems if they were not previously in the environment, such as chemical pesticides that accumulate in soil or water and cause pollution. ⁽⁴⁾

Second: Forms of environmental pollution by oil and gas:

The forms of pollution resulting from oil and gas vary, depending on the nature of the environment in which it is produced. There is pollution that affects water, air, and soil, as follows:

1- Air pollution

Air pollution is known as "the process of introduction of man directly or indirectly to energy materials in the air. Also, air has the effect over human health risk and cause damage to vital resources and ecosystems, and legitimate uses of its. ⁽⁵⁾"

As defined by the Iraqi Environmental Protection and Improvement Law, Article (1/ Eight) No. (27) of 2009, the article states that "the presence of any pollutant affecting the air in an unnatural quantity, concentration, or quality that leads directly or indirectly to harm humans or organisms other living things or the non-living components in which they are present".

The Egyptian Environmental Protection Law also defined it in Article (1 / IX) of Law 4 of 1994, air pollution as: "Air pollution is every change in the characteristics and specifications of natural air that results in a danger to human health and environment, whether this pollution is caused by natural factors or human activity including noise. ⁽⁶⁾"

Air pollution represents a dangerous stage in which the quantity and quality of pollutants exceed the environmental safety line. Examples of this type are what happened in the city of London in 1955, when it was covered by a thick cloud of smog for several days, which led to 4000 deaths. ⁽⁷⁾ Industry is one of the dangerous pollutants, especially air pollution, so depending on fossil fuels (coal, oil and natural gas) as a major source of energy. ⁽⁸⁾

Statistical reports prepared by the competent official authorities indicate that there is a continuous increase in the number of people infected with cancerous diseases from one year to another. The total number of cases of these diseases throughout Iraq has reached cases (18482) in 2010, then reached (20287) in 2011, then reach (21101) in 2012. This means that these diseases are in such large numbers. It is constantly increasing, which portends a great and imminent danger that threatens society as a whole. Therefore, it must stop and find the necessary treatment by treating the causes of this disease, which as said is the direct cause of air pollution, as oil and gas companies are one of the main reasons for its occurrence. ⁽⁹⁾

Through scientific and academic research conducted by the researcher in Kirkuk Governorate ⁽¹⁰⁾ as the results showed Statistics taken from Kirkuk Center tumors and blood diseases as shown in Figure (1) and (2).

While the statistics indicate that the number of deaths during the period 1-7-2020 until 1-3-2021 has reached 157 deaths. Putting that in mind data increases to (20) new cases which are recorded during every single week. The researcher conducts statistics and questionnaire in Kirkuk governorate because it is surrounded by factories and oil installations⁽¹¹⁾.

The studies dealt with calculating the cost of environmental deterioration resulting from air pollution in Kirkuk in northern Iraq (which is one of oil-producing cities in Iraq). The scientific methodology used by the World Bank was adopted in conducting studies, and the results of the study showed that the cost of environmental degradation from air pollution in Kirkuk amounted to (68.8) billion Iraqi dinars. It is equivalent to (12%) of the domestic gross product of Kirkuk in 2013. According to this study, the cost of environmental degradation represents 4.5% of the total cost of environmental degradation of air pollution throughout Iraq. It necessitates taking measures to address the sources of air pollutants in Kirkuk.⁽¹²⁾

Accordingly, we can give a simple definition of air pollution "that the presence of some impurities in the outside air in certain quantities and for a certain period so that they are harmful to human life, animals and plants and limit the quiet enjoyment of life and property and the exercise of human activity."

2- Water Pollution

Iraqi legislators did not specify in the law of environment protection and improvement what is intended to water pollution directly in No. 27 of 2009. Yet, Article (14/1) talks about some of the prohibited acts

in environment protection and improvement of the Iraqi law that " the conduct of verse remnants liquid domestic , industrial, service or agricultural to water resources interior surface subterranean or subterranean fields in Navy Iraqi only after Procedure needed to guarantee matching specifications in the national legislation environmental and international conventions " ([13]) .

Water pollution is defined in the Egyptian explicit environmental law as " the entry of materials or energy in the aquatic environment volitional way or involuntary directly or indirectly result in harm to living resources or non - living, or threaten human health or hinder water activities , including fishing and tourist activities or spoil sea water to use or detract from the enjoyment or alter their properties " ([14]) .

The 1982 Law of the Sea Convention, Article (1), Act 4/1, specified that "the pollution of the marine environment is caused by oil leaking from ships, atomic experiments at the bottom of the seas and oceans, disasters and marine collisions and sinking of oil tankers with the consequent severe damage to the marine environment." components of the marine environment. ⁽¹⁵⁾ "

Seas and oceans are enormous reservoirs of wealth and natural resources, and they represent 71 % of the Earth's area. Pollution of the marine environment constitutes the pollution of the entire globe. Man's direct or indirect release of energy materials into the marine environment, including estuaries result in harmful effects from them. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Law has approved the responsibility of the fertilizers industry companies , chemical products, forcing them to compensate fishing associations and fish farmers, as a result of pollution caused to fish and other aquatic because of the dumping of chemical pesticides, including compensation of fish value of the damaged neighborhoods, as well as purify and disinfect water which make them fit again for fish wealth. ⁽¹⁷⁾

The rise of this type of pollution in seadaily caused by oil tankers as they contribute to the largest amount of pollution either by sinking ships or transport of oil or during the washing of their tanks or in the stages of exploration. 2% oil in the globe is extracted from seas. Oil and its derivatives are environmental pollutants characterized by rapid spread on water surface and have a buffer layer that isolates the water from the air. This leads to a reduced amount of dissolved oxygen , which leads to the death of many animals. ⁽¹⁸⁾

Many national and international conventions dealt with pollution as indicated in Article 180 of the instructions ports Iraqi No. (1) in 1998. It indicates that "when disposing of oil, or water contaminated with petroleum products within the limits of the port, the ship or the boat is responsible and bear all cleaning expenses". In fact, the Iraqi legislator pays attention to this phenomenon as Iraq is an oil-producing country that is constantly exposed to pollution.

3- Soil Pollution

Soil pollution means the entry of pollutant substances into soil that cause a change in the physical, chemical or biological properties, which would eliminate the living organisms that inhabit soil and contribute to the process of decomposition of organic matter. ⁽¹⁹⁾

We can deduce the definition of soil pollution in Article (17) of the Iraqi Environmental Protection and Improvement Law No. (27) in 2009. It states that "any activity lead to directly or indirectly to soil degradation, deterioration or contamination. These effects lead to degrade soil production and aesthetic aspects only according to legislation " ([20]) .

The sources of soil pollution are many; chemical pollution result from the excessive use of fertilizers, pesticides, acid rain, radioactive materials, and in general, everything that pollutes water and air pollutes the soil. ⁽²¹⁾

Oil pollution affects soil and it is a dangerous source that help pollute it and transform its properties from strong, cohesive soil to disintegrate and unsuitable for agriculture. Oil acts as an impermeable barrier between soil and air particles to isolate soil and air from each other. The properties that perform its natural functions and its contents from living organisms and plants die. Thus the death of animals, crustaceans and eggs, cause a significant imbalance in the environment and spoil the soil. It is an important element in the agricultural environment, which can be counted a factor of prosperity and progress in Iraq. It is converted from the producer to the consumer and below zero in agricultural production ([22]).

Third: Sources of environmental pollution by oil and gas

The sources that pollute the environment with oil and gas vary, and oil and gas are the main source of these pollutants. Here, we suffice to mention three points in terms of the following:

1- Oil and gas refining:

The oil refining process is characterized by its high pollution capacity in terms of interaction and diffusion as it takes many forms and access to air, soil, fresh water, seas or oceans. ⁽²³⁾

Among the important effects of refining activities is known "Mixed Pollutant", and it is a mixture of (petrol, white oil and gasoline), which is produced by pumping cascade of oil in pipes ⁽²⁴⁾ .

In Iraq, fourteen fuel distillation refineries are distributed in the Iraqi governorates that operate with low refining methods. Some of them have exceeded their production average and are thus unable to produce clean fuel in accordance with international environmental standards. ⁽²⁵⁾

The academic and scientific studies carried out by the researcher in Kirkuk, according to “the Facilitating Mission Document” sent to the oil companies in the mentioned city ⁽¹²⁶⁾. The results, as the researcher noted north gas companies staff and employees of the security protection of the company drink milk in the morning and evening. They suffer breathing problems and inflammation of eyes, which indicates the presence of gases and toxins as a result of operating units and sorting processing liquid gas from other components. A significant number of civil refineries are rudimentary and do not have the simplest available safety or security conditions. Air is full of thick black smoke and the researcher observes that the region is dark due to smoke, soot and noise caused by those refineries. The primitive ones called “Al-Koura” and these are located in Jimin, Qarnjir and other areas. These refineries contribute a noticeable increase in environmental pollution.

2- Fires and explosions caused by oil and gas:

Explosions that generate burning oil and gas, as thick smoke of burning oil and gas of the hydrocarbon and aromatic materials, gases and soot, which have a significant harmful effect on health. On land, these materials cause diseases in the respiratory and digestive systems and cancers. and others. ⁽¹²⁷⁾

Crude oil tankers are exposed to different accidents such as collision, collision of ports or drowning accidents. These accidents lead to environmental disasters due to leak of huge amounts of crude oil to sea ([28])

The burning of Kuwaiti oil wells during the Gulf War in 1990 led to smoke rising to five thousand tons per day. Smoke blocks the sun's rays, polluting the atmosphere and lands and affect the life cycle of some marine creatures, including coral reefs. The war resulted in the largest oil leak in modern history, as the total amount of oil reached the Gulf water about five million barrels. Its direct impact extended a distance of 750 km in Al-Ahmadi port in Kuwait to Qatar through the Gulf of Bahrain. Still, environment in Kuwait suffer oil leak of these wells. ⁽¹²⁹⁾

In confirmation of the above, the researcher states “**in 2014, Iraq was affected by terrorist attacks and their control over one third of Iraq’s land. Factories, oil and gas companies, and transport lines between the provinces are located in these areas. This led to tampering, sabotage, theft, broken pipelines, oil thefts, explosion of fuel tanks, and oil leakage from pipelines to Tigris River. It cause dangerous environmental damage to human health and the environment**” .

3- Oil spills into the marine environment. ⁽¹³⁰⁾

Many oil-producing countries export to consuming countries by huge marine tankers, giant pipelines, or land transport trucks ⁽¹³¹⁾. Perhaps, the problems that accompany this process are the direct oil leakage through tanker accidents or explosion of wells, followed by the balance water used by these tankers in the return stage ⁽¹³²⁾. Many methods result in pollution emanating from oil and gas companies and the materials used in extraction of oil and gas.

Gas emissions, oil leakage, and other petroleum activities pave the way for environmental pollution ⁽¹³³⁾. Pollution due to leakage from tanker pipelines, leakage accidents can occur from pipelines that deliver crude oil to the last export ports for various reasons, including: Corrosion of pipes due to their obsolescence, and the lack of systems to protect against corrosion.

-Accidents of all kinds, such as the collision of transport means and other reasons.

-Oil liquid theft work, which is done by placing holes in the pipes.

-Military actions in times of war and acts of sabotage.

-Apart from accidents of pipe breakage, pipelines transporting petroleum products are exposed to a different type of pollution, which is the pollution resulting from mixing oil derivatives with each other, and this is what was previously referred to under the name “polluted mixture.”

Within the scope of oil leaks, effects related to oil leakage, which from a basic problem to have oil and its extraction ([34]), an example of this is: “**an accident occurred in the Indian city of Bhopal / Madhya state, a gas leakage occurred in 1984 that killed more than 3,500 people. A few of them survived and were seriously ill, and 25,000 of them died. Yet, those who were born after this incident, most of them suffering from mental and physical disabilities**” ([35]).

Conclusion:

It was found that the elements, forms and sources of environmental pollution with oil and gas are among the factors affecting the pollution of the environment. It is through the entry of polluting materials into the environment, which represents water, air and soil, or their entry because of a person. Many legal rules and the improvement of the Iraqi environment, and identified many agreements, including the Law of the Sea of 1982. The sources of environmental pollution are among the important substances that negatively affect the environment, whether it is oil and gas refining or fires, explosions and oil leaks.

Conclusions:

- 1- The environmental pollution caused by oil and gas is harmful. Oil and its residues cause environmental pollution, given the wide range of residues caused by these companies in this activity.
- 2- Modern oil and gas companies and the various risks and damages that accompany them have failed to achieve adequate protection for those affected.
- 3- Pollution represents a major threat to human life and environment.
- 4- Many agreements have emerged to limit pollution and determine the resulting responsibility.
- 5- The conventions in the field of marine pollution do not have an executive authority over the signatory countries, and they follow the moral, not the legal, in the implementation process.
- 6- The obvious shortcomings in environmental pollution legislation and policies that need to be amended and reformulated.

Recommendations:

- 1- Establishing a green area to reduce spread of dust and gases in the atmosphere.
- 2- Increasing the allocation of the agricultural sector to reduce the phenomenon of pollution.
- 3- The trend towards imposing environmental taxes to reduce environmental pollution and change behaviors leading to the use of non-renewable resources.
- 4- Work to educate people and impose laws to ensure a broader environment and its preservation .
- 5- Combating harm to environment by any means.

Margins:

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- ([3])Dr .Ahmed Abdel Karim Salama, Environmental Protection Law in Islamic Legislation, previous source, p. 10.

- ([4])Dr .Youssef Attari, International Law and Oil Pollution of the Marine Environment, Dirasat Journal, Nasr on the University of Jordan, Vol. 33, No. 1, 2006, p. 132.

-([5])Muhammad Abd al-Qadir al-Fiqih, The Environment.. Its Issues, Problems and Protection from Pollution, The Egyptian General Book Authority, 1999, p. 37.

-([6])See Article (1/9) of Law 4 of 1994.

-([7])The London newspaper "Middle East" has published that the national program on cancer in Iraq is in line with the directives of the World Health Organization. According to the statistics of the World Health Organization, we find that in 2016 cancerous diseases in Iraq amounted to 25,556 cancer cases, which is thus It is considered the second cause of death after heart disease. Research has attributed the cause of cancerous diseases in sweat to environmental pollution, including oil compounds and radioactive pollution.

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-([9])Iraqi Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization, Directorate of Environmental Statistics, Environmental Statistics Report, in Iraq (Natural Conditions - Health Indicators - Agricultural Indicators) for the year 2015, p. 75.

- ([10])Ministry of Health, Center for Oncology and Blood Diseases in Kirkuk Governorate, according to book No. 9359 dated 3/18/2021.

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([13])Article (14/1) of the Environmental Protection and Improvement Law No. (27) of 2009 stipulates that the following shall be prohibited:

First: Discharging any domestic, industrial, service or agricultural liquid wastes into the internal surface and ground water resources or the Iraqi marine areas except after carrying out the necessary treatments to ensure their compliance with the specifications specified in the national environmental legislation and international agreements.

The relevant binding relationship to the Republic of Iraq, and this includes all expenses, whether continuous, intermittent or temporary, and taking the necessary measures to prevent the arrival of pollution from land to the marine area, whether through water or air, directly from the coast, or from ships and aircraft.

Second: Connecting or draining the sewers of homes, factories and other activities to rainwater drainage networks.

Third: Throwing solid waste, animal excrement, remains, or waste into water resources.

Fourth: The use of toxic materials and explosives in hunting fish, birds and aquatic animals.

Fifth: Discharge of oil residues, fuel residues, or balancing waters of oil tankers to the internal surface waters or Iraqi marine fields, whether the discharge is from fixed stations, mobile sources, or from leaks resulting from loading operations.

Sixth: Any works that lead to the pollution of surface water resources as a result of exploiting their banks, except after the approval of the concerned authorities.

Seventh: Any actions that lead to pollution of the marine area as a result of exploration or exploitation of the regional seabed, its subsoil and the continental shelf, including confronting emergency pollution cases that result in damage to the marine environment in a manner that ensures compliance with national legislation and the principles and provisions of international law.

- ([14]) See Article (12 / 1) of Law No. 4 of 1994.

- ([15]) Convention on the Law of Sea 1982, Article 1 Force 04

([16]) - Dr .Badriya Abdullah Al-Owaidi, Commentary on a ruling on sea pollution with oil, the necessity of abandoning negligence as a basis for determining responsibility in pollution cases, Journal of Law and Sharia, Kuwait University, Year 3, Issue 1, March, 1979, p. 139

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- ([25]) Ahmed Mahmoud Saeed, An Extrapolation of the Rules of Civil Liability in Environmental Pollution Disputes, 1st Edition, Dar Al-Nahda, Al-Arabiya, 1994, pp. 61-64.

- ([26]) A field visit to the private refineries in the city of Kirkuk, according to the book No. 3/7/4287 on 8-12-2020, and the visit took place on 15-3-2021.

- ([27]) Dr .Muhammad Ali Hassoun, The State's Responsibility for the Damage of Environmental Pollution, 1st Edition, Dar Al-Fikr Al-Jami, Alexandria, 2014, 35, Muhammad Abdel Qader Al-Faqhi, The Environment: Its Issues, Problems and Protection from Pollution, Egyptian General Book Authority, 1999, p. 39 and beyond.

- ([28]) The tanker accident *Kasuga Maru* No. 01 that occurred in Japan on December 01, 1988. For more details about the accident, refer to p 41 cit op fipol : 1991 Rapport Annuel de.

- ([29]) Laura Adham, Criminal Protection of the Environment against the Dangers of Pollution, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Baghdad, 1999, p. 222

-(1) Perhaps oil accident that took place and which had a wide international profile was the ship "Tory Canyon". Some of the rocks and coral reefs located in the southwest of the British coasts. As a result of this accident, vast areas of sea water were polluted, extending to 320 kilometers from the western and southern coasts of Britain and bypassing it on the other side until it reached the French coasts, and the amount of oil that was mixed with the water was about 120 thousand tons. Consequently, many fish and birds were killed. Not every rescue attempt succeeded. The cost of the rescue amounted to about 5.2 million pounds .Refer to that incident Paul D. Bradly., Marine oil Leakage, Natural resources Journal. Vol, 140, July 1974, p.33.

(2) - Transfer of more than 2 billion tons annually by sea from global production for oil. 4000 tankers of oil roam the sea, this leads to some serious environmental accidents. In 90s, 5 millions tons of oil are thrown annually because of unloading conveyors. Then, amounts are decreased as a result of laws and systems of strict legislation that confirmed the strictness in an area to save the environment. Then, what do you pour? Conveyors in an offshore sea from waters balance and leftovers operations cleaning other no still in a border 12 one thousand tons in a year.

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